

ELIXIR Biodiversity,
Food Security and
Pathogens
2024-26
Work Plan

ELIXIR Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens 2024-2026 Work Plan

Abstract

In the priorities of the ELIXIR Scientific Programme 2024-2028, molecular science connecting biodiversity, food security, and pathogens has been identified as a societal challenge and scientific opportunity set as a core domain that shapes ELIXIR's activities. The Programme stresses that the application of molecular techniques is critical to understand the diversity and breadth of life on Earth. In other words, the diversity of life, rapidly changing climate, increasing contact between the natural world and humans can influence emerging infectious agents which impact not only humans, but also farmed animals, crops and wildlife.

The Commissioned Service contributes to that Priority through the provision of leadership, community engagement, and open project calls:

- Leadership and Strategy: A team drives strategy, supported by the ELIXIR Hub.
- Community Engagement: ELIXIR Community Members are engaged via meetings and calls.
- Pilot studies and Open Calls: Members submit projects aligned with the roadmap.

This effort connects the ELIXIR Communities and Nodes in their response to advances in biodiversity, food security and pathogens and enables these advances to contribute to wider research questions.

This document shows the work plan version as approved by the ELIXIR Board.

About this document

Authors

Tereza Manousaki¹, Cyril Pommier², Robert M. Waterhouse³, Physilia Chua⁴, Peter Maccallum⁴, Katharina Heil⁴, on behalf of the ELIXIR Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens priority area team⁵

- 1. Hellenic Centre for Marine Research, Institute of Marine Biology, Biotechnology & Aquaculture, Greece*
- 2. National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE), France*
- 3. SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics, Switzerland*
- 4. ELIXIR Hub, UK*
- 5. The complete list of contributors and their affiliations can be found in Appendix "Partner information"*

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by ELIXIR, the research infrastructure for life-science data as Commissioned Service 2024-SCIENCE-BFSP, part of the 2024-2028 ELIXIR Scientific Programme.

Contact

info@elixir-europe.org

ELIXIR

Wellcome Trust Genome Campus,

Hinxton,

Cambridgeshire

CB10 1SD

United Kingdom

Copyright notice:

© ELIXIR 2025

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution CC-BY licence version 4.0.

Contents

Abstract	2
About this document	3
Authors	3
Acknowledgements	3
Contact	3
Copyright notice:	3
Contents	4
1. Objectives and relation to the Scientific Programme	5
2. Partnership	6
3. Work Package descriptions	7
Work Package 1 - ELIXIR Strategy for Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens	7
Objectives	7
Description of Work	7
Work Package 2 - E-PAN: Enhancing pan-genome analysis in plants	10
Objectives	10
Description of Work	11
Outcomes & Impact	12
Work Package 3 - FAIRyMAGs - Optimising Metagenomics Assembled Genomes building: workflow finalisation, training material development, real data evaluation and resource allocation tool creation	14
Objectives	14
Description of Work	15
Outcomes & Impact	17
Work Package 4 - HARVEST: Handling and alignment of plant research FAIRification – value through the use of ELIXIR data Standards and Tools	19
Objectives	19
Description of Work	20
Outcomes & Impact	22
Work Package 5 - Odyssey: Connecting molecular and geographical biodiversity data	23
Objectives	23
Description of Work	24
Outcomes & Impact	27
Work Packages - Pilot studies	28
Work Packages - Open Call/Commissioned Services	28
Table of Deliverables and Milestones	29
Appendix: Partner information	31

1. Objectives and relation to the Scientific Programme

ELIXIR's Programme 2024-2028 is organised around four Priorities, of which the first is a focus on science - to "enable scientists to access and analyse life science data". This priority outlines three Ambitions, of which the second is to "Mobilise and integrate life science data to support transnational research programmes in biodiversity, food security and pathogens", the technologies and data types which underpin all of ELIXIR's activities. As outlined in the ELIXIR Scientific Programme 2024-2028,

"The areas of biodiversity, food security and pathogens represent critical societal challenges that Europe must address over the next decade, and which are strongly enabled by the application of molecular sciences and other data-intensive disciplines. The importance of these scientific areas in contributing to societal challenges is also widely recognised by major transnational and national funding bodies and is reflected in their research strategies."

To work towards this goal ELIXIR needs to understand the molecular techniques used in this area, establish a clear roadmap, identify key internal partners and nourish connections to external partners, e.g. other Research Infrastructures, and develop our presence in the national as well as international funding landscape.

To reach this goal this Commissioned Service will make three main contributions to ELIXIR:

- Leadership and strategy development
- Community engagement
- Open call projects and/or pilot studies for the Priority Area.

We aim to contribute to solutions in the area by starting with a coordinated effort across ELIXIR Nodes and beyond, enabling the following.

Leadership: An advisory team of three experts has been identified to drive this ambition together with ELIXIR Hub support. Concrete activities are described as an activity in WP1 "ELIXIR Strategy for Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens".

Community engagement: It is key to involve the ELIXIR Community in this effort. Hence another activity in WP1 focuses on engaging with ELIXIR members, to gain a wide overview of the theme, incentivise community building and start establishing our network of experts related to biodiversity, food security and pathogens. To do so different approaches will be used: A theme kick-off, midterm and final meeting combined with regular interactions, e.g. through regular cross-theme video-conference calls. Outcomes of these activities, combined with the consolidated leadership activities will incentivise knowledge exchange and inform the writing of the ambition roadmap.

Pilot studies and/or Open Call Projects call for the community: Once the theme roadmap has been defined ELIXIR members are best placed to work towards identified aims. A third task in WP1 will be to work with the vast expertise of ELIXIR members and prepare Open Calls for projects to be submitted. ELIXIR members will hence contribute towards the identified roadmap, with a diverse range of projects of different sizes and breadth of scope. Collaborations across disciplines (e.g. involving several ELIXIR Communities) will be incentivised and rewarded.

The open call is expected to run during 2024 allowing for projects to start in 2025, and again in 2026 for projects in the later parts of the Programme. Selected pilot studies may be developed in advance or in parallel with the Open Call projects.

2. Partnership

Contributors to the work programme are listed in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Overview of involved institutions. Leads highlighted in **bold**.

Node	Institution	Abbreviation
CH	Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics (Lead)	CH-SIB
FR	National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE) (Lead)	FR-INRAE
GR	Centre for Marine Research HCMR (Lead)	GR-HCMR
ELIXIR	ELIXIR Hub	ELIXIR-HUB
BE	Flanders Institute for Biotechnology	BE-VIB
DE	University of Freiburg	DE-FREIBURG
DE	Research Center Jülich GmbH, Jülich	DE-FZJU
DE	Helmholtz Center Munich	DE-HMGU
DE	Leibniz Institute of Plant Genetics and Crop Plant Research	DE-IPK
EMBL	EMBL's European Bioinformatics Institute	EMBL-EBI
FR	CNRS - Institut français de bioinformatique (IFB)	FR-IFB
FR	National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE/Emphasis.fr)	FR-INRAE
GR	Democritus University of Thrace	GR-DUTH
GR	Centre for Research and Technology Hellas	GR-CERTH
IT	University of Bari*	IT-UNIBA
NL	Wageningen University & Research	NL-WUR
NO	Norwegian University of Life Sciences	NO-NMBU
PT	NOVA University of Lisbon (Institute of Chemical and Biological Technology)	PT-ITQB NOVA
SI	National Institute of Biology (NIB)	SI-NIB
UK	Rothamsted Research	UK-ROTHAMSTED
UK	University of Oxford (Oxford e-Research Center)	UK-UNIOXF
Total		

*Institution not receiving any funding in CoS

3. Work Package descriptions

Work Package 1 - ELIXIR Strategy for Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens

WP 1	Lead Partner: CH-SIB
	Start month- End month: M01-M36
WP Partnership	
CH-SIB - Robert Waterhouse (Lead)	
FR-INRAE - Cyril Pommier (Lead)	
GR-HCMR, Tereza Manousaki (Lead)	
ELIXIR-HUB - Katharina Heil (Coordinator), Physilia Chua	

Objectives

- Develop and document background understanding of the developments in Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens Research which will impact the application of molecular techniques.
- Write a Strategy to guide ELIXIR's priorities and decision making when participating in activities in support of Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens Research.
- Develop a Roadmap for ELIXIR direct investments and participation in projects and consortia in this area.
- Engage with ELIXIR Communities and gather their requirements and proposed contributions to the Roadmap.
- Build active working relationships with partner Research Infrastructures and international consortia.
- Guide the selection and development of new ELIXIR Communities relevant to Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens.
- Through pilot studies, demonstrate ways of working across the Communities connected to the theme.
- Through open calls, leverage the ELIXIR network to develop approaches and technologies to solve problems of pan-European working.
- Update the Work Plan for the next period, 2027-2028.

Description of Work

This work package will allow the leadership team to coordinate a programme of work across the theme, through three activities - strategy development, community engagement, and running pilots & open calls and/or pilot studies.

Members from all Nodes are invited to contribute to the shaping of the scientific theme/ambition. They will get together regularly to develop a roadmap and later on become participants and applicants in the open project call. Wide engagement is necessary to consider distinct national roadmaps, activities ongoing in active projects and to bring together knowledge and coordinate ongoing activities linked to the Theme across Europe and the world. A core activity will be to scope ELIXIR's possible contribution to the area, with regards to molecular techniques and data (management, stewardship, ...) without directly competing with spaces already covered by others, e.g. other Research Infrastructures.

Activity 1: ELIXIR Strategy for Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens Research (*Leads: Rob Waterhouse (CH), Cyril Pommier (FR), Tereza Manousaki (GR); Members: Katharina Heil (ELIXIR-HUB), Physilia Chua (ELIXIR-HUB). M1-M36.*)

Working in partnership with Hub staff, Hub Management Team, ELIXIR Heads of Nodes and ELIXIR Scientific Advisory Board, the co-leads of the theme will develop a Strategy connecting the ELIXIR Services, Platforms, Communities and Projects to ensure effective coordination of efforts for the benefit of research scientists working within the basic science areas of biodiversity, food security and pathogens and for those who depend on these technologies for translational, environmental, societal or industrial impact.

This work will involve being available for regular meetings with ELIXIR Members (for example the monthly Programme TC and the ELIXIR All Hands Meeting) and in support of ELIXIR outreach to partner Research Infrastructures and international partners, in addition to regular meetings of participants in this Commissioned Service funded through Pilot Studies or Open Calls and/or Pilot Studies.

The co-leads and Hub will develop a Strategy and a multi-annual Roadmap for investments, updated annually, and will consult widely to develop a renewed Work Plan for 2027-2028 and input into the 2029+ Programme.

Activity 2: Engagement with the ELIXIR Communities (*Leads: Rob Waterhouse (CH), Cyril Pommier (FR), Tereza Manousaki (GR); Members: Katharina Heil (ELIXIR-HUB), Physilia Chua (ELIXIR-HUB). M1-M36.*)

ELIXIR’s engagement in Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens Research will be primarily facilitated by the ELIXIR Communities working in this area. The theme co-leads will meet regularly to engage in dialogue with the Community co-leads and Community membership, promote and support their individual activities, and discuss the Open Calls and other funding opportunities.

Direct Community engagement and input into the Strategy and Roadmap will be enabled by face to face cross-community workshops organised throughout the project. Two face to face workshops will be organised (approximately 25 people each). The Hub will support the organisation of these workshops, while the co-leads will guide the content, the topics covered, invitations to external partners, and reporting of outcomes.

With regards to Communication and Dissemination this activity hence relies on the members to advocate for the theme, use their existing connections to bring knowledge to this forum and enable the best possible understanding of the landscape.

Activity 3: Open calls for Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens Research (*Leads: Rob Waterhouse (CH), Cyril Pommier (FR), Tereza Manousaki (GR); Members: Katharina Heil (ELIXIR-HUB), Physilia Chua (ELIXIR-HUB). M5-M36.*)

The main focus of the funded effort for the theme will be Work Packages funded through an Open Call process. The co-leads and Hub will draft call text, write review criteria, and run Open Calls - one during 2024 for projects to be implemented in 2025-2026, one during 2026 for projects to be funded during the next period 2027-2028.

These calls will be the opportunity for ELIXIR Communities to take a lead on the development of new data management or analysis capabilities, integration of existing resources to meet particular cross-domain challenges, or the investigation of the impact new classes of computational technology or new experimental data types on ELIXIR’s Services and Membership. Successful projects may combine multiple ELIXIR Communities and ELIXIR Services and align them with the developments of the ELIXIR Platforms and partner externally-funded projects.

The Hub and co-leads will provide an initial review of the quality and impact of the projects funded through the Open Calls, and summarise their contribution in the final Report.

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D1.1	Report and Roadmap on Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens in ELIXIR 2024-2025	CH-SIB	M13
D1.2	Report and Roadmap on Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens in ELIXIR 2025-2026	FR-INRAE	M25

D1.3	Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens Research 2027-2028 Work Plan	GR-HCMR	M30
D1.4	Final Report 2024-2026	CH-SIB	M36
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M1.1	2024 Open Call for Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens	FR-INRAE	M03
M1.2	Cross-Community workshop on Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens	CH-SIB	M09
M1.3	2026 Open Call for Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens	GR-HCMR	M27
M1.4	Cross-Community workshop on Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens	GR-HCMR	M33

Work Package 2 - E-PAN: Enhancing pan-genome analysis in plants

WP 2	Lead Partner: BE-VIB
	Start month- End month: M13-25
WP Partnership	
BE-VIB, Klaas Vandepoele Lead (WP and Activity 2 and Activity 4)	
DE-HMGU, Heidrun Gundlach Lead (Activity 1)	
UK-ROTHAMSTED, Keywan Hassani-Pak Lead (Activity 3), Member (Activity 4)	
DE-IPK, Uwe Scholz Member (Activity 1 and Activity 2)	
DE-FZJU, Sebastian Beier, Member (Activity 1)	
PT-ITQB NOVA, M. Margarida Oliveira, Member (Activity 1 and Activity 4)	
SI-NIB, Kristina Gruden, Member (Activity 1 and Activity 4)	

Objectives

The adaptive differences between genotypes of the same species can only be explained by exploring genomic diversity through pan-genomics. The sequencing and assembly of pan-genomes no longer pose significant scientific challenges, but the subsequent data integration and exploration is hampered by a lack of standards and tools. For example, a simple comparison of the sequences of 44 potato genomes (Tang et al., Nature 2020) would not lead to any significant insights. However, the investigation of gene Presence Absence Variation (PAV) and structural rearrangements highlighted loci of interest to link intra-species genotypic with phenotypic diversity.

The global objective of the E-PAN project is to accelerate the use of pan-genome data through advances in data quality control, curation, integration, and visualisation. These objectives can be placed on different axes, which can be progressed in parallel:

- Methods for ensuring high-quality pan-genome data. In order to ascertain that PAVs are biological and not technical artefacts, the need for quality control (QC) and standardisation is clear. Solely using BUSCO (Seppey et al., Methods Mol Biol 2019) for estimating genome and gene space completeness of pan-genomes will miss nearly all intra-species differentiation. Therefore new standards and methodologies, benchmarked against real data from a broad phylogenetic species selection, are required. This will result in new guidelines and tutorials for pan-genome QC.
- Computation and standardised reporting of gene-based PAVs and structural variants. Apart from implementing efficient and scalable algorithms to quantify different types of structural variants, the obtained results will be shared in a standardised manner between the different plant resources, resulting in better access to pan-genomics results for diverse plant species.
- Visualisation and integration of pan-genomes and derived results. Current approaches to visualising pan-genomes do not automatically lead to easily-interpretable results using the current set of data integration tools. Therefore, we aim to evaluate and prototype a set of visualisation modules that can be (re)used in multiple plant databases. These will connect complementary resources and enhance the extraction of biological knowledge for key agricultural species.

Based on the expertise of all partners involved and the numerous interactions with different stakeholders involved in data generation, tool development, as well as biological interpretation of plant genome information, we will address these objectives in four Activities:

Activity 1. Development and evaluation of standards for quality control and sharing of plant pan-genomes;

Activity 2. Improvement of algorithms to characterise pan-genome dynamics and data visualisation;

Activity 3. Connecting and sharing pan-genome information across different plant platforms;

Activity 4. Community building to foster interactions between (ELIXIR) plant genome platforms.

These Activities align with the overall activities of the ELIXIR Plant Sciences Community, especially on the aspect of developing community resources (PLAZA) and enabling future opportunities for wider integration. New guidelines for the creation of pan-genome resources and the workshop will also address training aspects, which are a central theme of ELIXIR. Building on E-PAN's experience and best practices, this will create new tools and web resources that will simplify and standardise the handling of pan-genome data.

Description of Work

Within the E-PAN project we aim to enhance pan-genome data analysis by focusing on data quality control, curation, integration, and visualisation. While a lot of work has been done on representing species' genetic diversity during/after assembly, for example by constructing complex genome graphs, most biologists have a strong interest in understanding how this intra-species diversity affects the presence/absence of specific genes and their associated functions. However, publicly available tools and data standards helping to address these questions are scarce. Consequently, this project primarily focuses on the gene-based comparative analysis of plant pan-genomes. By employing specific data visualisations (e.g., Activity 2), we also seek to establish links between gene PAV and the corresponding genomic DNA sequences. By focusing on a selection of species of major importance for agriculture and plant research (barley, potato, wheat, rice and the model *Arabidopsis*), the project will have both a societal and industry impact, narrowing the divide between research institutions and the crop breeding companies.

Activity 1: Development and evaluation of standards for quality control and sharing of plant pan-genomes (3.5 PMs) (Leads: Heidrun Gundlach (DE); Members: Klaas Vandepoele (BE), Sebastian Beier (DE), Uwe Scholz (DE), M. Margarida Oliveira (PT), Kristina Gruden (SI), Keywan Hassani-Pak (UK). M13-M19).

ELIXIR Germany will take the lead in developing the necessary standards and tools to evaluate and assess the quality of pan-genomes. ELIXIR Belgium will provide the necessary expertise for tool development and integration of the tools in existing workflows (e.g., NextFlow).

Pan-genome data exchange standardisation and development will be a shared responsibility of ELIXIR Germany, Belgium, and UK. ELIXIR Slovenia and Portugal will deliver pan-genomes, perform the necessary tests and feedback, and draft tutorials. Facilitating data exchange, and how to make the data FAIR, is one of the key selling points of the project, and as such will require the combined effort of all partners. By iteratively improving the proposed solutions, and testing them out using real data, we hope to come to a common standard that all parties can consent to.

Tasks:

T1.1: Data quality control standardisation (M1-M3);

T1.2: Data quality control implementation (M3-M6);

T1.3: Data exchange standardisation and development (M3-M4).

Activity 2: Improvement of algorithms to characterise pan-genome dynamics and data visualisation (2.25 PMs) (Leads: Klaas Vandepoele (BE); Members: Uwe Scholz (DE). M16-M20).

ELIXIR Belgium will be the leading partner in the additional development of tools and algorithms for the characterization of pan-genome dynamics at the gene level. These developments will be stand-alone based on shared data exchange principles as developed within Activity 1, but will also be integrated within existing data platforms (i.e. FRINGE, <https://bioinformatics.psb.ugent.be/plaza.dev/fringe> and the extension of PanBARLEX, <https://panbarlex.ipk-gatersleben.de/> to a general tool for more species/crops).

Furthermore, prototyping different pan-genome visualisations (e.g., Panache [Tang et al., *Bioinformatics* 2021], SyRI-Barley as an interactive web tool for SyRI results [Goel et al., *Genome Biology* 2019]) and associated data protocols will be a shared development of ELIXIR Belgium and Germany.

Tasks:

T2.1: Tool development PAV detection (M5-M6);

T2.2: Tool development data visualisation(s) (M6-M7).

Activity 3: Connecting and sharing pan-genome information across different plant platforms (1.25 PMs)
(Leads: Keywan Hassani-Pak (UK); Members: Klaas Vandepoele (BE). M19-M22).

ELIXIR UK, assisted by ELIXIR Belgium, will be the leading partner for the prototyping of data formats to exchange general pan-genome analysis results and integrate these in different platforms (e.g., PLAZA/FRINGE, KnetMiner). ELIXIR UK will also integrate new pan-genome information in KnetMiner knowledge graphs.

Tasks:

T3.1: Integration pan-genome information in PLAZA/FRINGE and KnetMiner (M8-M9).

Activity 4: Community building to foster interactions between (ELIXIR) plant genome platforms (1.25 PMs)
(Leads: Klaas Vandepoele (BE); Members: M. Margarida Oliveira (PT), Kristina Gruden (SI). M22-M25).

A one-day event will be organised (by ELIXIR Belgium) where the results of this project and new opportunities for collaborative research will be discussed. We will invite both ELIXIR as well as external stakeholders to get a broad representation of plant genome experts. Based on the preparatory meetings in drafting this proposal, it became clear there is a lot of critical mass and momentum in the ELIXIR Plant Sciences Community to boost plant pan-genome research and address key challenges. In addition, an online workshop will be organised to showcase the developed tools and practical use cases and exchange training material (ELIXIR Slovenia). Taken together, the E-PAN project combines the effective knowledge and data resources of multiple and complementary research groups within the ELIXIR Plant Sciences Community and will give a strong boost to pan-genomics in the international plant research community. While the project focuses on a selection of crop and model species as a starting point, the acquired know-how on pan-genome analysis and standards can subsequently be used for projects within the bio-conservation and biodiversity research communities, where genome sequencing is generating new resources with unprecedented scope and coverage (e.g., Earth BioGenome project, Darwin Tree of Life project).

Tasks:

T4.1: Organising of plant pan-genome meeting and online workshop (M10-M12)

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D2.1 (Activity 1)	Develop standards for assessment of pan-genome completeness	DE-HMGU	M16
D2.2 (Activity 2)	Computational pipelines to assess pan-genome data quality and characterise gene-based structural variation within pan-genomes	BE-VIB	M19
D2.3 (Activity 2)	Prototyping and evaluation of data visualisations to represent pan-genome dynamics	DE-IPK	M20
D2.4 (Activity 3)	Development of API calls and sharing of bulk-downloads to exchange pan-genome information across different platforms (PLAZA/FRINGE and KnetMiner) for the selected plant species	UK-Rothamsted	M22
D2.5 (Activity 4)	Training materials based on crop-specific use cases deposited at TeSS	PT-ITQB NOVA	M25
D2.6 (Activity 4)	Online workshop to showcase the developed tools and practical use cases	SI-NIB	M25

Outcomes & Impact

We use the term “outcomes” and “impacts” as defined by the ELIXIR community, based on their respective spheres of influence and interest. Whereas “deliverables” are within the sphere of control of the project, “outcomes” cover effects outside the direct control of the ELIXIR partners, and “impacts” cover structural changes in the economy and society.

We envision multiple positive outcomes of this project on the research community in general, and the genome assembly/annotation community specifically. By adopting the standards and following the guidelines that we propose, future pan-genome projects will have overall higher quality and accuracy. Pan-genome QC metrics are currently quasi non-existent, leading to researchers independently trying to create new standards. Thus, by homogenising the QC, and eliminating redundant work, we also expect an impact on the field of genome research: faster QC, fewer issues during publication review, and standardised output. These new standards and guidelines will also further streamline the processes of pan-genome data submission and integration in ELIXIR Core Data Resources such as ENA and Ensembl Genomes. All together the impact will result in significant savings in terms of both time and money.

We are expecting constructive feedback from researchers. It is to be expected that within our QC proposal, there will be inaccuracies or missing options for specific needs. Therefore having an open discussion with the community at large (WP4) will be of strategic interest for long-term support of the standards. Thus, we hope that E-PAN might kick-start the creation of a global community of researchers that can update the standards as needed. Such communities already exist, for example for plant phenotyping (EMPHASIS) and orthology (QuestForOrthologs). Consequently, ELIXIR can take up a leading position in this regard, and promote the adoption of these QC guidelines. Multiple other ELIXIR Communities, which may lack the expertise of the groups within this research proposal, may also benefit from this. For example, the guidelines can be implemented within Galaxy as a new workflow, the Biodiversity Community may employ the QC guidelines when sequencing new genomes, etc. Furthermore, publishing these guidelines under the banner of ELIXIR will enhance the visibility of both the ELIXIR organisation itself, as well as the data standards that ELIXIR develops and promotes.

We expect that the integration of new pan-genome data types in flagship ELIXIR platforms such as PLAZA, a RIR, and KnetMiner, will result in additional interest and an increasing number of new users from academia as well as industry. Thus, the implementation of new approaches and algorithms to evaluate and analyse pan-genomes, and new ways to visualise the data, might result in additional industrial income further down the line for these Node services.

The final impact of the project will be years downstream when breeding companies use the progress made in this project to enhance the quality of their in-house sequenced pan-genomes, and standardise their workflows around a global set of guidelines. This in turn should lead to optimizations of genome data mining, and improved crop selection and breeding techniques.

Work Package 3 - FAIRyMAGs - Optimising Metagenomics Assembled Genomes building: workflow finalisation, training material development, real data evaluation and resource allocation tool creation

WP 3	Lead Partner: DE-FREIBURG
	Start month- End month: M13-M30
WP Partnership	
DE-FREIBURG Paul Zierep, Lead (WP and Activity 1 and Activity 3), Member (Activity 2 and Activity 4)	
FR-IFB Bérénice Batut, Lead (Activity 2 and Activity 4), Member (Activity 1 and Activity 3)	
IT-UOB - Giuseppe Defazio, Member (Activity 1 and Activity 4), Bruno Fosso, Member (Activity 1 and Activity 4)	
EMBL-EBI, Martin Beracochea, Member (Activity 3 and Activity 4), Santiago Sanchez, Member (Activity 3 and Activity 4)	

Objectives

The proposed project aligns closely with the objectives and priorities outlined in the ELIXIR Biodiversity, Food Security & Pathogens Scientific Priority Area, as articulated in the ELIXIR 2024-2028 Scientific Programme. This priority area within ELIXIR aims to mobilise and integrate genetics and omics data to support research programs in biodiversity, food security, and pathogens, including agriculture and aquaculture research.

The proposed project directly addresses these challenges by advancing metagenomics research, a field that plays a pivotal role in understanding and mitigating the impacts of biodiversity loss, enhancing food security, and combating pathogens in agricultural and environmental contexts. This project will be the first to offer a high-computation end-to-end MAGs workflow through Galaxy, incorporating FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles to benefit the research community.

The project's objectives are designed to contribute to the overarching goals of the ELIXIR Biodiversity, Food Security & Pathogens Scientific Priority Area:

- **Metagenomics Building Workflow Design, Implementation, and Evaluation:** To date, researchers face challenges in independently analysing Metagenome-Assembled Genomes (MAGs) due to technically demanding workflows and high computational requirements. These issues will be addressed by implementing the workflows in Galaxy, a platform that facilitates easier execution and management of bioinformatics analyses, coupled with the computing resources of public servers. By finalising a Galaxy workflow for building MAGs, the project will empower researchers to investigate uncultured genomes with respect to biodiversity monitoring, pathogen detection, and agricultural research. This workflow will facilitate the analysis of microbial communities in diverse ecosystems, providing insights into biodiversity dynamics and pathogen prevalence. Through the evaluation of MAGs generated by the workflow using simulated and real-world data from diverse environments (atmosphere, marine, and cow gut microbiomes), the project will provide valuable insights into the performance and applicability of metagenomics approaches across different research domains and enable the adaptation of the workflows and its parameters to specific and potentially unexplored environments.
- **Accessibility and Reusability:** The integration of the developed workflow with WorkflowHub will ensure its accessibility, reusability, and extension by the broader research community. This aligns with ELIXIR's goal of fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing within the life sciences community, enabling researchers to leverage existing tools and resources to address pressing societal challenges. Galaxy workflows can be reused and adapted by using specific tools (and tool versions),

databases, and workflow logic using a graphical workflow builder. To the best of our knowledge, this simplicity is unmatched by current MAGs workflows.

- **Training and Education:** The creation of FAIR educational materials hosted on the Galaxy Training Network and their delivery via a hybrid workshop will support capacity building and skills development in metagenomics analysis. It will equip researchers with the necessary expertise to utilise the workflow effectively and contribute to building a skilled workforce capable of harnessing molecular sciences for building new genomes. The generated training will help researchers to understand the workflows in detail and hence also allow for additional contributions to further development.
- **Resource Allocation:** The investigation of computational resource requirements for executing the workflow on various input datasets addresses the practical challenges associated with scaling metagenomics analysis. By developing a tool for estimating and allocating resources based on input data characteristics (such as kmer counts), the project will support efficient and cost-effective MAG construction (also for non-Galaxy based workflows), facilitating broader adoption of metagenomics approaches in research and decision-making processes related to data management. The proposed tool could be extended to other resource-intensive computations, significantly decreasing the environmental impact of large parallelized workflows.

In summary, the proposed project exemplifies a concerted effort to harness molecular sciences and data-intensive approaches to address critical societal challenges related to biodiversity conservation, food security, and pathogen management. By aligning with the goals and priorities of the ELIXIR Biodiversity, Food Security & Pathogens Scientific Priority Area, the project will contribute to advancing scientific knowledge and supporting evidence-based decision-making in these vital domains.

Description of Work

Activity 1: Workflow Design, Implementation, and Evaluation (3.5 PMs) (*Leads: Paul Zierep (DE); Members: Bérénice Batut (FR), Giuseppe Defazio (IT), Bruno Fosso. M13-M30.*)

Activity 1 aims to refine, optimise, FAIRify, and evaluate the Galaxy-based workflow prototype for constructing Metagenomics Assembled Genomes (MAGs). Taxonomy classification and genome annotation will be integrated. The workflow parameters will be optimised for improved efficiency, accuracy, and scalability. To ensure the accessibility and reusability of the developed workflow, documentation, metadata, and test data will be prepared following FAIR principles. Through submission to the Intergalactic Workflow Commission (IWC) and WorkflowHub, the workflow will be made discoverable and interoperable, with continuous updates and maintenance to reflect enhancements and feedback. Validation will be conducted using the CAMI benchmarking infrastructure to ensure the workflow's robust performance against established standards. Therefore the CAMI infrastructure will also be integrated into Galaxy, facilitating FAIR benchmark methodology, for the community. To assess the performance of the developed workflow, 3 real-world metagenomics datasets from various environments will be gathered. The workflow will be used on those datasets to generate Metagenomics Assembled Genomes (MAGs) which will then be evaluated in collaboration with domain experts to ensure their accuracy and relevance.

Tasks:

T1.1: Refine the Galaxy-based workflow prototype for building Metagenomics Assembled Genomes (MAGs), integrate taxonomy classification and genome annotation of MAGs in the workflow, and optimise workflow parameters and configurations to enhance efficiency, accuracy, and scalability (M13 - M18);

T1.2: Prepare documentation, metadata, and test data following IWC and WorkflowHub guidelines, submit the developed workflow IWC and WorkflowHub, ensuring compliance with FAIR data principles for discoverability and interoperability, and continuously update and maintain the workflow on IWC and WorkflowHub to reflect improvements and address user feedback (M19 - M30);

T1.3: Validate the workflow using CAMI benchmarking infrastructure (datasets, tools) (M21 - M22);

T1.4: Gather real-world metagenomics datasets from diverse environments (atmosphere, marine, and cow gut microbiomes), execute the developed workflow on the collected datasets to generate Metagenomics Assembled Genomes (MAGs), and evaluate the generated MAGs with experts from the domain (M21 - M27).

Activity 2: Training Material Development and Delivery (2.0 PMs) (Leads: *Bérénice Batut (FR)*; Members: *Paul Zieryep (DE)*. M16-M30).

Activity 2 aims to empower researchers with the skills necessary for effective utilisation of the developed workflow by creating comprehensive training materials tailored to diverse expertise levels. Collaboration with experts from the ELIXIR Microbiome and Galaxy Communities will ensure the accuracy, relevance, and accessibility of these materials. They will be available through the Galaxy Training Network, findable on ELIXIR TeSS, and taught during one online workshop, that will be broadly advertised within the ELIXIR Communities and related European projects, to reach a global audience.

Tasks:

- T2.1: Develop a tutorial tailored for researchers with varying levels of expertise (M16-M20);
- T2.2: Collaborate with experts from the ELIXIR Microbiome and Galaxy Community to ensure the accuracy, relevance, and accessibility of training materials (M20-M24);
- T2.3: Publish training materials on the Galaxy Training Network, making them freely accessible to the global research community (M25-M25);
- T2.4: Organise and conduct one online workshop using the developed training material (M26-M30).

Activity 3: Computational Resource Allocation Tool Development (4.5 PMs) (Leads: *Paul Zieryep (DE)*; Members: *Bérénice Batut (FR)*, *Martin Beracochea (EMBL-EBI)*, *Santiago Sanchez (EMBL-EBI)*. M14-M28).

Activity 3 aims to streamline the computational resource allocation process for metagenomic assemblies by analysing input data characteristics and developing a machine-learning model to predict resource requirements. EMBL-EBI will provide extensive information about compute requirements for assemblies generated using the MGnify pipeline. The implementation of a user-friendly tool based on this model together with rules assigned via the Galaxy Total Perspective Vortex (TPV) - a framework that allows the assignment of dynamic rules for Galaxy job execution - will enable to accurately estimate and allocate computational resources for executing the workflow on diverse datasets. The upper boundary of the resources available for the MAGs workflow is given by the European Galaxy instance, which currently provides 8 nodes with 1TB RAM and 36 cores and 1 node with 2TB RAM and 60 cores.

Tasks:

- T3.1: Analyse the needed computational resources for metagenomics assembly using data provided by the MGnify platform and k-mer profiles of the input data (M14-M18)
- T3.2: Build a Machine-learning model to predict the needed computational resources for the assembly based on the k-mer profile (M19-M22)
- T3.3: Implement a tool for using this model to predict computational resources required for executing the workflow on different input datasets (M23-M27)
- T3.4: Integrate the resource allocation tool and rules for resource allocation in Galaxy using Galaxy Total Perspective Vortex (TPV) (M27-M28)

Activity 4: Engagement & Dissemination (2.0 PMs) (Leads: *Bérénice Batut (FR)*; Members: *Paul Zieryep (DE)*, *Giuseppe Defazio*, *Bruno Fosso (IT)*, (*Martin Beracochea*, *Santiago Sanchez (EMBL-EBI)*. M15-M30).

Activity 4 focuses on coordination and dissemination of the project. We will organise a hackathon in Freiburg (Germany) to discuss workflow demands, benchmarking procedures and the implementation of the resource allocation tool. This event will include all consortium partners and will also openly invite members from ELIXIR communities and European projects (e.g. NFDI4Microbiota, PHENET). The project outcomes will be communicated to the scientific community by writing a manuscript for peer-reviewed publication and submitting contributions to relevant scientific conferences for presentation. This will ensure that the developed workflow, resource allocation tool, and training materials reach a wide audience, fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange in the field of metagenomics research.

Tasks:

- T4.1: Organise and conduct hackathon in Freiburg (M15-M22);
- T4.2: Write a manuscript for a peer-reviewed journal (M15-M30);
- T4.3: Submit to present the work at a relevant scientific conference (M28-M30).

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D3.1 (Activity 1)	Workflow available on UseGalaxy Europe and UseGalaxy France servers as well as published on IWC and WorkflowHub.	DE-FREIBU RG	M20
D3.2 (Activity 1)	Assessed MAGs and their quality for the 3 selected real-world datasets	DE-FREIBU RG	M27
D3.3 (Activity 2)	Tutorial hosted on the Galaxy Training Network and visible on ELIXIR' TeSS	FR-IFB	M25
D3.4 (Activity 3)	Machine-Learning model registered on DOME registry and implemented to predict needed computational resources of metagenomic assembly tools for given input data and rules integrated into Galaxy Total Perspective Vortex (TPV)	DE-FREIBU RG	M28
D3.5 (Activity 4)	Blogpost summarising the hackathon outcomes	DE-FREIBU RG	M22
D3.6 (Activity 4)	Abstract for a talk at a conference submitted	FR-IFB	M30
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M3.1 (Activity 1)	Prototype and metadata of Galaxy workflow	DE-FREIBU RG	M20
M3.2 (Activity 1)	Recovered MAGs for selection of 3 real-world datasets.	DE-FREIBU RG	M24
M3.3 (Activity 2)	Online workshop	FR-IFB	M30
M3.4 (Activity 3)	Data from MGnify with computational resources used for metagenomics assembly	DE-FREIBU RG	M18
M3.5 (Activity 4)	Hackathon in Freiburg	DE-FREIBU RG	M22
M3.6 (Activity 4)	Preprint submitted on BioRxiv	FR-IFB	M30

Outcomes & Impact

The proposed project is expected to yield significant outcomes and impact across multiple dimensions, including scientific advancement, capacity building, and societal benefit. At the core of these outcomes is the development and dissemination of a robust metagenomics workflow tailored for building Metagenomics Assembled Genomes (MAGs) using the Galaxy platform, alongside associated training materials and computational resource optimization. These outcomes will contribute to the overarching goal of leveraging molecular sciences and data-intensive approaches to address pressing challenges in biodiversity, food security, and pathogen management.

1. Scientific Advancement:

- a. The finalisation of the Galaxy workflow for MAGs building will represent a significant advancement in metagenomics research, providing researchers with a standardised, FAIR, and user-friendly tool for analysing complex microbial communities.

- b. By conducting rigorous evaluations of MAGs generated by the workflow using real-world datasets, the project will enhance our understanding of microbial diversity, pathogen dynamics, and ecological processes across diverse environments. The envisioned MAGs benchmark framework will combine the MAGs workflow with benchmarking capability, allowing for a continuous benchmark of updated workflow versions, adapted to various sequencing and sample conditions.
 - c. The project's focus on FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data analysis using Galaxy ensures that research outputs are readily discoverable, accessible, and reusable, fostering transparency, reproducibility, and collaboration within the scientific community.
- 2. Capacity Building:
 - a. The creation of FAIR training materials hosted on the Galaxy Training Network will empower researchers with the skills and knowledge necessary to effectively utilise the developed workflow for metagenomics analysis.
 - b. An online workshop conducted as part of the project will further enhance capacity-building efforts, enabling researchers to leverage molecular data for biodiversity monitoring, agricultural research, and pathogen surveillance.
- 3. Societal Benefit:
 - a. The availability of a production-ready metagenomics workflow and associated resources will enable researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders to make informed decisions regarding biodiversity conservation, food security enhancement, and pathogen management.
 - b. By facilitating the analysis of microbial communities in agricultural and environmental contexts, the project supports efforts to enhance crop productivity, mitigate disease outbreaks, and promote sustainable land management practices.

Work Package 4 - HARVEST: Handling and alignment of plant research FAIRification – value through the use of ELIXIR data Standards and Tools

WP 4	Lead Partner: DE-FZJU
	Start month- End month: M13-M24
WP Partnership	
DE-FZJU, Sebastian Beier, Lead (WP, Activity 4) , Member (Activity 1 and Activity 2)	
FR-INRAE, Cyril Pommier, Lead (Activity 3) , Member (Activity 1, Activity 2 and Activity 4)	
DE-IPK, Daniel Arend, Lead (Activity 1) , Member (Activity 2, Activity 3 and Activity 4)	
EMBL-EBI, Timothee Cezard, Lead (Activit 2) , Member (Activity 1, Activity 3 and Activity 4)	
UK-UNIOXF, Philippe Rocca-Serra , Member (Activity 2)	
NL-WUR, Matthijs Brouwer , Member (Activity 1)	
FR-INRAE (Emphasis.fr), Isabelle Alic , Member (Activity 1, Activity 2 and Activity 4)	

Objectives

We aim to improve existing resources with established data standards (MIAPPE, ISA, ARC, RO-Crate) to enhance plant data access and reusability over a project duration of 12 months. This will be done by (i) producing exemplar datasets using RO-Crate and MIAPPE, (ii) documenting this work to ease further adoption and outreach among biologists and computer scientists, and (iii) integrate those reference datasets in existing data repositories and services (FAIDARE data portal). This work will rely on the extension and connection of existing ELIXIR resources and services: RO-Crate data exchange package (<https://doi.org/10.3233/DS-210053>), the MIAPPE plant phenomics data standard (www.miappe.org), the RDMKit and FAIR Cookbook and the FAIDARE plant data portal. Most of those are registered in the Service Delivery Plans of national Nodes. We will also take advantage of established data repositories such as e!DAL-PGP, Zenodo and Dataverse (Recherche Data Gouv).

We will further develop several existing resources of the ELIXIR Plant Sciences Community. Initially, we will extend and FAIRify at least two existing datasets from the DROPS and AGENT European projects, selected for their availability for public reuse, richness and representativeness of phenotypic and geospatial data for two major crop species: maize and wheat. The project outcome will facilitate the reuse of this data, but above all serve as example and documentation of machine actionable data sharing using RO-Crate and MIAPPE. They will therefore be listed in the documentation of the standards as reference datasets and thus contribute to its adoption. Secondly, we will extend the plant related documentation on the RDMKit. Finally, we will expand the capabilities of FAIDARE and increase the number of indexed datasets.

We will connect technical resources (RO-Crate and MIAPPE) as well as data services and repositories (FAIDARE, e!DAL-PGP, Dataverse, Zenodo) used for crop data. For this we will rely on results produced within previous BioHackathons (<https://doi.org/10.37044/osf.io/7y2jh>) and Implementation Studies (FONDUE, Increasing).

We will improve the existing guidelines available on the RDMKit and FAIR Cookbook and enable outreach and adoption through webinars.

This project is well aligned with the past and future activities of the ELIXIR Plant Sciences Community, in particular in terms of findability, sustainable access and reuse of data, the development of community recommendations and building of cross domain data linking and integration in particular between phenomics and other omics data. The latter, developed in collaboration with the European EMPHASIS infrastructure for

plant phenotyping, relies on the sharing of common data resources identifiers (e.g. cultivar and germplasm identifiers) between omics data repositories, such as EVA for genotyping, and phenomics datasets.

Description of Work

Activity 1: FAIRification of existing datasets (2.0 PMs) (Lead: Daniel Arend (DE); Members: Cyril Pommier (FR), Isabelle Alic (FR), Timothee Cezard (EMBL-EBI), Sebastian Beier (DE), Matthijs Brouwer (NL). M13-20).

In this Activity, we will focus on the FAIRification of existing datasets, in particular the DROPS (<https://doi.org/10.15454/lASSTN>) and AGENT datasets (<https://dx.doi.org/10.5447/lipk/2023/20>) as well as selected datasets from other important crops (see below). We will also extend our efforts to other databases, e.g. datasets published in PHIS (<http://www.phis.inrae.fr/>) and support export of RO-Crates from EVA studies.

Main objectives:

1. Quantify the work necessary to produce machine-actionable FAIR datasets using RO-Crate from existing datasets.
2. Provide reference examples of standards adoption that demonstrate the FAIR process for both data producers and data repositories using RO-Crate.

Tasks:

T1.1: Assess the selected datasets to understand their structure, metadata requirements and current level of standardisation.

T1.2: Develop a detailed plan for converting these datasets to RO-Crate format to ensure compliance with FAIR principles.

T1.3: Conduct conversion of the selected datasets to RO-Crate and identify best practices and potential challenges.

T1.4: Adopt RO-Crate packaging in EVA as a use case for data repositories.

At the end of Activity 1, we will have a clear understanding of the effort required to produce machine-actionable datasets and lay the groundwork for subsequent work packages focussing on guidelines, adoption and dissemination of FAIR practices within the Plant Sciences.

Activity 2: Updating the documentation of standards, RDM guidelines, and checklists (3.5 PMs) (Lead: Timothee Cezard (EMBL-EBI); Members: Cyril Pommier (FR), Isabelle Alic (FR), Daniel Arend (DE), Sebastian Beier (DE), Philippe Rocca-Serra (UK). M18-M24).

The RDMKit 'Plant Sciences' page is used as the entry point to the RDM documentation used by the Community and beyond. It already includes documentation of plant data standards and tools. This Activity will update them in collaboration with the ELIXIR RDM Community to include an explicit and user-friendly decision tree that guides users to the relevant RDM resources. We will create and update the dataset FAIRification recipes referenced by the RDMKit. Finally, we will include relevant Activity 1 results in the MIAPPE standard documentation and generate updated mappings between other data standards (ISA, RO-Crate, BrAPI, Bioschemas). Activity 2 will provide researchers with a comprehensive resource within the RDMkit that will facilitate informed decisions and adoption to aid findability, reproducibility and reusability thanks to data standards, by presenting mappings and practical use cases for MIAPPE, BrAPI, ISA, Bioschemas and RO-Crate. In addition, the documentation and sample data of the standards will be expanded and harmonised with the latest versions.

Main objectives:

1. Expand the 'Plant Sciences' domain page in RDMkit (https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/plant_sciences) as a one-stop-shop for Plant Science researchers seeking information on data standards and practices.
2. Develop and maintain links to and from relevant external websites (e.g. ELIXIR Plant Science Community, miappe.org, brapi.org, etc...) that provide detailed resources on data standards and related topics.
3. Update existing documentation and checklists to include Activity 1 results.

Tasks:

T2.1: Review and update existing documentation and checklists for dataset FAIRification.

T2.2: Design and implementation of a decision tree interface that guides researchers through the selection of appropriate dataset FAIRification guidelines based on their specific requirements.

T2.3: Update and development of mappings and guidelines for the integration of MIAPPE, BrAPI, ISA, Bioschemas and RO-Crate standards.

T2.4: Cross reference the RDMKit 'Plant Sciences' domain page to and from relevant websites (ELIXIR Plant Sciences Community page, FAIRsharing collection page <https://fairsharing.org/4741>) to increase its visibility and improve the number and quality of referenced resources. Recipes, in the form of Jupyter notebooks, will be added to the FAIR Cookbook.

T2.5: Write preprint on plant data FAIRification.

Activity 3: Extend the plant data discovery portal FAIDARE with new RO-Crate resources (1.75 PMs)

(Lead: Cyril Pommier (FR); Members: Daniel Arend (DE), Timothee Cezard (EMBL-EBI). M13-M24).

The FAIDARE (<https://urgi.versailles.inra.fr/faidare/>) crop and agronomy data discovery portal is already able to index data resources using BrAPI or through data discovery files in a web folder (<https://urgi.versailles.inrae.fr/faidare/join>). The existing data indexing service will be extended to process RO-Crates for datasets. This enhancement will significantly improve the findability, accessibility and granularity of valuable datasets within FAIDARE. By the end of Activity 3, we will have significantly expanded the scope and usability of FAIDARE by including RO-Crate-enabled datasets, thereby improving the overall discoverability and accessibility of plant and agricultural data. This work will help to consolidate FAIDARE as the European plant data portal for researchers looking for FAIR data in the field of Plant Sciences and Agronomy.

Main objectives:

1. Extend FAIDARE's indexing capabilities to include RO-Crate data containers to ensure they are searchable and accessible via the FAIDARE data portal.
2. Improve the indexation of repositories such as PLANTdataHub, Dataverse, Zenodo and other relevant data repositories that provide RO-Crate data containers.
3. Demonstrate practical benefits of the FAIRification of dataset using RO-Crate.

Tasks:

T3.1: Development and implementation of methods for indexing RO-Crate data containers within the FAIDARE platform.

T3.2: Establish connections and integration pathways with external repositories hosting RO-Crate datasets to enable seamless data discovery and access via FAIDARE.

Activity 4: Dissemination and Training (1.25 PMs) *(Lead: Sebastian Beier (DE); Members: Cyril Pommier (FR), Isabelle Alic (FR), Daniel Arend (DE), Timothee Cezard (EMBL-EBI). M18-M24).*

This Activity will disseminate the project results and provide comprehensive training to promote awareness and adoption of data standards and FAIR practices in the Plant Science community. At the end of Activity 4, we maximise the impact of the project by effectively disseminating knowledge and providing a webinar that empowers researchers to incorporate FAIR data principles into their work, thereby increasing FAIR data management and accessibility in the field of Plant Sciences.

Main objectives:

1. Presentations at conferences (including posters and talks) to showcase the project results, share best practice and engage with the wider scientific community.
2. Conduct a webinar to present the project results and demonstrate the adoption of FAIR practices in Plant Data Management.

Tasks:

T4.1: Prepare and deliver presentations at relevant conferences to disseminate project findings, raise awareness and encourage collaboration within the plant science community.

T4.2: Organising and conducting a webinar for researchers, breeders and data managers to present and demonstrate the project results and to offer FAIR practices in Plant Data Management for adoption, building on material contributed to the FAIR Cookbook.

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
-------------	-------------	-------------------------	-------------

D4.1 (Activity 1)	Generate exemplary datasets as reference RO-Crates	DE-IPK	M18
D4.2 (Activity 2)	RDMkit pages updated and cross referenced on relevant websites	EMBL-EBI	M20
D4.3 (Activity 2)	Preprint on plant data FAIRification	DE-FZJU	M24
D4.4 (Activity 3)	Extension of FAIDARE Indexing (use PLANTdataHUB as use case), extension to other relevant repositories prepared (Dataverse, Zenodo)	FR-INRAE	M24
D4.5 (Activity 4)	Webinar on guidelines	DE-FZJU	M24

Outcomes & Impact

The HARVEST project aims to significantly advance data management in plant research by integrating specific standards (such as MIAPPE and BrAPI) with generic standards (ISA and RO-Crate). It builds on previous initiatives such as ELIXIR IS FONDUE & INCREASING, H2020 AGENT, HE AgroServ & PHENET and the ongoing NFDIs DataPLANT, FAIRagro and NFDI4Biodiversity.

Past activities, including BioHackathons, have highlighted the need for more robust exemplification of MIAPPE with reference datasets and increased adoption of MIAPPE within the RO-Crate framework. The HARVEST project addresses these challenges by undertaking a sustained effort over an extended period of time.

The expected outcomes of HARVEST include easier adoption of best practices, improved data reusability and better data discoverability in plant sciences. This will help to streamline data management processes and promote collaboration and knowledge sharing. Additionally, HARVEST will harmonise information on FAIRification of plant data in various resources, including the ELIXIR Plant Sciences Community site, FAIRsharing and others, with a central entry point in the RDMkit. Updates and enhancements to platforms such as RDMkit, FAIR Cookbook, FAIRsharing and related resources will contribute to a coherent and accessible framework for FAIRification of plant data and its management. For instance, the FAIR Cookbook will be enriched by incorporating Jupyter notebooks to demonstrate FAIRification and showcase how such processes will look like in practice.

The impact of the HARVEST project goes beyond ELIXIR by facilitating the dissemination and adoption of ELIXIR-promoted interoperability standards and initiatives in the field of research data management. HARVEST will provide exemplar datasets from DROPS, AGENT and other important crop species, providing a demonstration for other projects like PHENET, thus encouraging broader adoption of FAIR practices for data producers. Similarly, HARVEST will also demonstrate the potential of RO-Crate exports of datasets from EVA studies and serve as an example for other repositories to adopt similar practices in the future. One of the advantages of having experimental data and metadata in an RO-Crate is also the possibility of direct import into workflow systems such as the Galaxy platform (usegalaxy.eu), allowing researchers to run bioinformatics pipelines directly on the FAIRified data. In addition, the preprint publication, the webinar session and the central entry point at RDMkit will play an important role in raising awareness and promoting the adoption of FAIR data principles and standards beyond the ELIXIR Plant Sciences Community. We will communicate this progress to relevant stakeholders within AgBioData, the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the Research Data Alliance (RDA) and actively engage them during the development. These efforts will facilitate broader engagement and collaboration between the different communities in the field of research data management.

Work Package 5 - Odyssey: Connecting molecular and geographical biodiversity data

WP 5	Lead Partner: GR-DUTH, NO-NMBU
	Start month- End month: M13-M30
WP Partnership	
GR-DUTH, Aristotelis C. Papageorgiou, Lead (WP and Activity 4) , Member (Activity 1, Activity 2 and Activity 3)	
NO-NMBU, Helle Tessand Baalsrud, Lead (WP) , Member (Activity 1, Activity 3 and Activity 4), Thu-Hien To, Member (Activity 1 and Activity 3), Lars Grønvold, Member (Activity 2 and Activity 3), Gareth Benjamin Gillard, Member (Activity 2 and Activity 3), Arturo VeraPonce de Leon, Member (Activity 3)	
GR-HCMR, Evangelos Pafilis, Lead (Activity 1 and Activity 2) , Member (Activity 3 and Activity 4), Nefeli Venetsianou, Member (Activity 1 and Activity 2), Alexios Loukas, Member (Activity 1 and Activity 2)	
GR-CERTH, Fotis Psomopoulos, Lead (Activity 3) , Member (Activity 2 and Activity 4), Nikolaos Pechlivanis, Member (Activity 1 and Activity 2 and Activity 3), Anastasia Anastasiadou, Member (Activity 1 and Activity 2 and Activity 3)	

Objectives

The project's scope is to develop a web portal that will enable researchers, stakeholders and citizens to navigate the molecular biodiversity data in a user-friendly and informative way based on the geographic information of Greece and Norway. This interface will become a pilot application with the perspective to further develop the resources of the Biodiversity Community and the ELIXIR Nodes, enabling wider integration of more European countries .

Specific objectives:

- Utilising and connecting existing databases, web portals and applications harbouring and handling molecular biodiversity data, along with species geospatial, ecological and phenotypic data, as well as available information about threats, challenges, conservation status and in-place policies. The main challenge will be aligning and harmonising the metadata across sources. For example, there is no consistency in the geo/location metadata across disparate repositories and databases, especially in terms of granularity (e.g. there are cases where location only indicates country, and other cases where the exact GPS coordinates are mentioned). In this project we will try to harmonise this information so that data retrieved from multiple sources (such as GBIF and ENA) can be used in a seamless manner. To this end, we will also explore state-of-the art NLP methods (incl. LLMs). However, we won't be assessing the validity of the metadata, such as location data, i.e. we won't perform error correction.
- Pilot the implemented framework by connecting resources, expertise and know-how from two different ELIXIR Nodes, representing two biodiversity rich regions in Europe (Nordic and Mediterranean) as well as differences in government and infrastructure relevant for molecular biodiversity, by utilising the existing networks in Greece (Molecular Biodiversity Greece Community - MBGC) and Norway (The Norwegian Biodiversity Working Group - NBWG), as hubs for exchange and meet. This will significantly strengthen and expand the biodiversity related efforts of the two Nodes.
- Leveraging the experience from the Norwegian and Greek ELIXIR Nodes to create and share training materials to increase the use of genetics and omics data in combination with geographical data both in basic and applied sciences such as conservation biology.

- Enhancing the availability of the existing documentation about the spatial genomic diversity patterns to biodiversity researchers, conservation scientists and decision makers and therefore bridging the gap between these groups.
- Increasing awareness about the importance of genomic information for biodiversity at all levels, by providing comprehensive and accessible information.
- Providing a use case that will benefit the ELIXIR Biodiversity Community, as it can be expanded and connected with various ELIXIR Platforms (Data, Training, Tools), Communities (Microbiome, Plant Sciences, Food and Nutrition), as well as ELIXIR's external partners and projects.

This proposal specifically targets the core goals of the BFSP Priority Area mission, by providing a framework to make biodiversity molecular data more accessible to the wider community while enabling full customisation to support the particular needs of a Node or a Community. While there are major databases and efforts in place that aim to provide this harmonised access to high-quality data, there is still a lot of information that is being deposited in non-specialized databases (such as ENA), or even only in national and local repositories. The main output of this effort will be to implement a reusable framework, that can be deployed by individual users and/or institutions, that will enable metadata curation, semi-automated harmonisation, and visualisation of data from multiple user-defined sources, while also offering the creation of AI-ready datasets as export function.

Odyssey will be leveraging the interoperability standards for metadata in the underlying repository, while taking advantage of the existing Core Data Resources (such as the European Nucleotide Archive - ENA: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena>) and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility - GBIF: <https://www.gbif.org/>) as primary data providers. Specifically, the framework implemented in this project, closely following the ELIXIR Tools Software Best Practices, will enable individual users to directly query ENA and GBIF, in order to retrieve molecular biodiversity data relevant to their study. Although the data itself will not be stored locally, the main advantage of this framework is to enable local storage and curation of the respective metadata, by offering a seamless and semi-automated way of annotating. Beyond ENA and GBIF, we will be reviewing additional sources of data, such as BGE (and its connections to iBOL/BOLD/Earth Biogenome Project). Ultimately, the effort of this project will be analogous to GoAT (<https://goat.genomehubs.org/>), connecting molecular metadata from multiple sources and optimising both query and visualisation methods to align to a nation's community requirements. Finally, the framework will be demonstrated using the two involved Nodes (GR/NO) as pilot cases, but the ambition is for this framework to be used across all ELIXIR Nodes.

Moreover, all software produced under this project will closely follow the Tools Platform software best practices recommendations, and adhere to the expectations set by projects such as ELIXIR-STEERS and EVERSE for high quality software. Additionally, the project will establish a continuous feedback mechanism with the Biodiversity Community, to ensure that the final output will be adopted and re-used by the individual Nodes - a process that will include organising at least one workshop / hackathon for members of ELIXIR to participate and contribute. Finally, the project will fully build on the existing efforts of the MBGC and NBWG in Greece and Norway.

Description of Work

Activity 1: Connecting the Dots - Data Gathering (2.25 PMs) (*Lead: Evangelos Pafilis (GR), Helle Tessand Baalsrud (NO); Members: Aristotelis C. Papageorgiou (GR), Thu-Hien To, Arturo VeraPonce de Leon (NO), Alexios Loukas, Nefeli Venetsianou (GR), Nikolaos Pechlivanis, Anastasia Anastasiadou (GR). M13-M30.*)

We will mine data and metadata for Greece and Norway from two different databases, ENA and GBIF. ENA contains various sequence data from barcodes to full genomes, sometimes with geographical location. GBIF contains biodiversity occurrence data, of which only some of it refers to the geographical location of molecular data. We will retrieve and connect these types of data, which will be overlaid on maps and organised in terms of taxonomic groups, populations, habitats and geographical regions. This will include harmonising geographical metadata from ENA, as different formats have been used.

Incrementally more data sources will be explored. These can include datasets from Biodiversity Genomics Europe (BGE) as well as retrieval of pertinent biodiversity literature from BiodiversityPMC. By adding geographical reference to molecular data, the integration of further geospatial, ecological and phenotypic data could be investigated as a preparation for future functionality. Maps of protected areas as well as land cover charts, for example, could offer key information about threats, challenges, conservation status and in-place policies.

Tasks:

T1.1: Plan with ENA and GBIF the gaps of information that can be filled.

T1.2: Connect to up-to-date biodiversity literature information and metadata mining for Greece and Norway.

Activity 2: Application Design and Implementation (3.60 PMs) (Lead: *Evangelos Pafilis (GR), Lars Grønvold (NO)*; Members: *Aristotelis C. Papageorgiou, Fotis Psomopoulos, Nikolaos Pechlivanis, Anastasia Anastasiadou (GR), Gareth Benjamin Gillard (NO), Alexios Loukas, Nefeli Venetsianou (GR)*. M13-M30).

The members of the proposal will define the key functionalities to be facilitated by the portal. Such domain expertise in collaboration with software developers will be translated into an application, aiming at answering to the needs of the biodiversity community in a simple-to-use way, excluding the need for advanced knowledge of querying databases.

Working in parallel with and utilising data sourced from Activity₁ a dedicated unified repository will be implemented, that will contain the harmonised data as well as additional fields necessary for further study (geographical coordinates, sequences, etc). Additionally, a graphical interface will be developed, named Odyssey, to delve into biodiversity information. Odyssey will undergo development to ensure accessibility to users. This development will be divided into backend and frontend design and development. To this end, enhancements applied to the existing prototype (accessible at shinyapps.io/odyssey) to seamlessly integrate Activity₂ front-end components designed for the presentation of the collected data. R Shiny will serve as the primary web application technology. The related software components will be openly available.

Tasks:

T2.1: Adding geographical context (WG84 coordinates, altitude) on database content, such as sequence data from ENA and biodiversity occurrence data from GBIF.

T2.2: Designing and implementing backend functionalities including tasks such as integrating Activity₁ data sources to efficiently store and manage molecular biodiversity data, implementing database schemas, optimising server-side processes, and integrating data cleaning processes to ensure data quality and integrity.

T2.3: Implementing frontend features including User Interface Refinement within the Odyssey web platform through intuitive navigation elements, descriptive statistics, and visualisations, alongside R Shiny Implementation to incorporate dynamic and interactive features via modular design, while ensuring Open Accessibility through GitHub to foster transparency and collaboration within the research community.

Activity 3: Dissemination and Training (3.15 PMs) (Lead: *Fotis Psomopoulos (GR), Arturo VeraPonce de Leon (NO)*; Members: *Evangelos Pafilis (GR), Aristotelis C. Papageorgiou (GR), Nikolaos Pechlivanis (GR), Anastasia Anastasiadou (GR), Helle Tessand Baalsrud, Lars Grønvold, Gareth Benjamin Gillard, Thu-Hien To (NO)*. M13-M30).

Dissemination, training and promotion actions, inviting users from the biodiversity research and applied conservation community in Greece and Norway. These will include:

- One kickoff online meeting and workshop announcing Odyssey and describing the functions to members of MBGC in Greece and NBWG in Norway, including also stakeholders (national and local conservation agencies).
- A scientific communication section in the Odyssey portal, supported by a channel on an open-access platform with demonstration and promotion video material.
- Open-access publications, presentations in biodiversity related conferences and meetings.
- Training material, produced and distributed following the FAIR principles and demonstrating Odyssey, its underlying machinery and its use, presented within relevant postgraduate programmes in Greece and Norway.
- Complementary to the automated methods of Activity₁, Activity₂, and on a need-only basis, georeference information for selected molecular datasets, will be further improved by community member curation. An online datathon will be organised to this end.
- Joint meetings with other ELIXIR Nodes and Communities / Platforms / Focus Groups. Specifically, and in order to strengthen the planned connection to ENA and GBIF, we will ensure that representatives from these resources will be invited to attend and contribute to at least one of these events.

Tasks:

T3.1: Showcase application and promote best practices for taxonomy and geographical data annotation when working with sequence data. Host training material online with Activity3 implementation.

T3.2 Create a public repository (e.g GitHub) with manuals and tutorials about using Odyssey to explore biodiversity as training material using FAIR principles.

T3.3 Develop a workshop showing the application of Odyssey with real data to the biodiversity community. The workshop will be streamed online to reach a wider audience.

Activity 4: Project Management (1.50 PMs) (Lead: Aristotelis C. Papageorgiou (GR), Helle Tessand Baalsrud (NO); Members: Evangelos Pafilis (GR), Fotis Psomopoulos (GR). M13-M30).

This Activity aims to coordinate the research team scientifically and administratively, implement the project's tasks and activities within the time frame, manage the project's finances and the software produced. These activities involve coordinating the project implementation by assessing the outputs based on the objectives, tracking the budget and possible changes, resolving conflicts and creating a risk management plan. The deliverables and milestones will be constantly checked to follow the programme schedule.

Moreover, a dedicated in-person workshop open to the entire community will be organised in the first half of the project, in order to push forward the development process (Activity1/Activity2), as well as establish an outline of the expected training material.

Tasks:

T4.1: Personnel exchange for training and collaboration, meetings, publications, reports

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D5.1 (Activity 1)	Report on the overview of relevant molecular biodiversity data in Greece and Norway	GR-HCMR	M30
D5.2 (Activity 2)	Back-end (database, schema, etc)	NO-NMBU	M30
D5.3 (Activity 2)	Front-end (shiny app, GitHub repo)	GR-CERTH	M30
D5.4 (Activity 3)	Run a virtual training event	GR-CERTH	M29
D5.5 (Activity 4)	Final project report	GR-DUTH	M30
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M5.1 (Activity 1)	Successfully implemented queries to ENA and GBIF	GR-HCMR	M18
M5.2 (Activity 2)	First demo of the Odyssey framework	NO-NMBU	M24
M5.3 (Activity 3)	Training material prepared and delivered in GitHub	GR-CERTH	M24
M5.4 (Activity 4)	Organise an open community event to demonstrate the new resource and its features getting feedback on the user requirements	NO-NMBU	M27

Outcomes & Impact

Odyssey's ambition is to serve as a pivotal tool in bridging gaps within biodiversity research, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and connecting scientific endeavours with conservation efforts. By making molecular biodiversity data accessible to researchers, stakeholders, and the public, this tool will facilitate informed decision-making, ultimately promoting conservation practices. Below are concrete outcomes and impact.

Outcomes

- Overview of molecular biodiversity data connected to geographical metadata in Norway and Greece.
- "Odyssey", an application to visualise, query and research relevant molecular data on a geographical map. This application will be a prototype developed for Norway and Greece, with the goal of expanding this effort to encompass the entire world.
- Strengthening of biodiversity related activities in Elixir-NO and Elixir-GR

Impact

- Science: Odyssey will have a profound impact on the scientific community as one of the main obstacles in molecular biodiversity research is to connect and harmonise different types of data. This is not a trivial matter, and by developing a web portal in the form of a user-friendly interface that allows federated searches of molecular databases and geographical databases will facilitate increased scientific output in this growing field.
- Biodiversity monitoring and conservation: There is currently an increase in the use of molecular data to catalogue and monitor biodiversity across the world, which is especially important to gain insights into understudied taxonomic groups and ecosystems. Odyssey will provide a user-friendly tool to study the geographical prevalence of molecular data, which could be used to better harness existing data as well as inform stakeholders which taxa or geographical regions with significant gaps.
- The Biodiversity Community - ELIXIR: Collaboration and cooperation between Nodes with distinct needs and expertise is an integral theme to Odyssey, fostering complementarity and knowledge exchange within the ELIXIR network. By design, the implemented framework will enable direct reuse and adoption by various communities across the Nodes, strengthening networks and fostering collaboration with strategic partners. By involving diverse stakeholders and leveraging existing initiatives (e.g., by inviting experts from different ELIXIR Nodes to meetings and workshops at all stages of the project), Odyssey enhances the capacity of the ELIXIR Biodiversity Community to address complex challenges and advance molecular biodiversity research on a transnational scale.
- Society: The main mission of Odyssey is to lower the barrier and facilitate biodiversity research, by harnessing molecular data in conjunction with geographic information and making the respective data available to the wider community. By integrating diverse datasets and employing advanced visualisation methods, it promises to enable a more in-depth understanding of molecular biodiversity in regions of interest - and always depending on the community it serves.

Additional work packages will be added to this work plan (with additional participants from across the Nodes) through amendments to this document over the lifetime of this study, anticipated as follows:

Work Packages - Pilot studies

One or more pilot studies may be proposed during the remainder of the project. Subject to Board approval, 1-3 Work Packages of 12 months' duration, may be added to this Work Plan by amendment.

New Communities formed within the theme of Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens can be funded as a Pilot Study.

Work Packages - Open Call/Commissioned Services

Four additional Work Packages, starting on 01 Jan 2025, have been added to this Work Plan in response to the 2024 Open Call, by amendment, after Board Approval.

Work packages related to subsequent Open Calls will be added in 2026 as required within the agreed funding limits.

Table of Deliverables and Milestones

Deliverable / Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M1.1	2024 Open Call for Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens	FR-INRAE	M03
M1.2	Cross-Community workshop on Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens	CH-SIB	M09
D1.1	Report and Roadmap on Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens in ELIXIR 2024-2025	CH-SIB	M13
D2.1	Develop standards for assessment of pan-genome completeness	DE-HMGU	M16
M3.4	Data from MGnify with computational resources used for metagenomics assembly	DE-FREIBURG	M18
D4.1	Generate exemplary datasets as reference RO-Crates	DE-IPK	M18
M5.1	Successfully implemented queries to ENA and GBIF	GR-HCMR	M18
D2.2	Computational pipelines to assess pan-genome data quality and characterise gene-based structural variation within pan-genomes	BE-VIB	M19
D3.1	Workflow available on UseGalaxy Europe and UseGalaxy France servers as well as published on IWC and WorkflowHub.	DE-FREIBURG	M20
M3.1	Prototype and metadata of Galaxy workflow	DE-FREIBURG	M20
D2.3	Prototyping and evaluation of data visualisations to represent pan-genome dynamics	DE-IPK	M20
D4.2	RDMkit pages updated and cross referenced on relevant websites	EMBL-EBI	M20
D2.4	Development of API calls and sharing of bulk-downloads to exchange pan-genome information across different platforms (PLAZA/FRINGE and KnetMiner) for the selected plant species	UK-Rothamsted	M22
D3.5	Blogpost summarising the hackathon outcomes	DE-FREIBURG	M22
M3.5	Hackathon in Freiburg	DE-FREIBURG	M22
M3.2	Recovered MAGs for selection of 3 real-world datasets.	DE-FREIBURG	M24
D4.3	Preprint on plant data FAIRification	DE-FZJU	M24
D4.4	Extension of FAIDARE Indexing (use PLANTdataHUB as use case), extension to other relevant repositories prepared (Dataverse, Zenodo)	FR-INRAE	M24
D4.5	Webinar on guidelines	DE-FZJU	M24
M5.2	First demo of the Odyssey framework	NO-NMBU	M24

M5.3	Training material prepared and delivered in GitHub	GR-CERTH	M24
D1.2	Report and Roadmap on Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens in ELIXIR 2025-2026	FR-INRAE	M25
D2.5	Training materials based on crop-specific use cases deposited at TeSS	PT-ITQB NOVA	M25
D2.6	Online workshop to showcase the developed tools and practical use cases	SI-NIB	M25
D3.3	Tutorial hosted on the Galaxy Training Network and visible on ELIXIR' TeSS	FR-IFB	M25
M1.3	2026 Open Call for Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens	GR-HCMR	M27
D3.2	Assessed MAGs and their quality for the 3 selected real-world datasets	DE-FREIBURG	M27
M5.4	Organise an open community event to demonstrate the new resource and its features getting feedback on the user requirements	NO-NMBU	M27
D3.4	Machine-Learning model registered on DOME registry and implemented to predict needed computational resources of metagenomic assembly tools for given input data and rules integrated into Galaxy Total Perspective Vortex (TPV)	DE-FREIBURG	M28
D5.4	Run a virtual training event	GR-CERTH	M29
D1.3	Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens Research 2027-2028 Work Plan	GR-HCMR	M30
D3.6	Abstract for a talk at a conference submitted	FR-IFB	M30
M3.3	Online workshop	FR-IFB	M30
M3.6	Preprint submitted on BioRxiv	FR-IFB	M30
D5.1	Report on the overview of relevant molecular biodiversity data in Greece and Norway	GR-HCMR	M30
D5.2	Back-end (database, schema, etc)	NO-NMBU	M30
D5.3	Front-end (shiny app, GitHub repo)	GR-CERTH	M30
D5.5	Final project report	GR-DUTH	M30
M1.4	Cross-Community workshop on Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens	GR-HCMR	M33
D1.4	Final Report 2024-2026	CH-SIB	M36

Appendix: Partner information

Table 2. Partner information

Institution	Contact Name
CH-SIB	Robert M Waterhouse ORCID
FR-INRAE	Cyril Pommier ORCID
GR-HCMR	Tereza Manousaki ORCID
ELIXIR-HUB	Katharina Heil ORCID , Physilia Chua ORCID
BE-VIB	Klaas Vandepoele ORCID
DE-FREIBURG	Paul Zierp ORCID
DE-FZJU	Sebastian Beier ORCID
DE-HMGU	Heidrun Gundlach ORCID
DE-IPK	Daniel Arend ORCID , Uwe Scholz ORCID
EMBL-EBI	Martin Beracochea ORCID , Santiago Sanchez ORCID , Timothee Cezard ORCID
FR-INRAE (Emphasis.fr)	Isabelle Alic ORCID
FR-IFB	Bernce Batut ORCID
FR-INRAE	Cyril Pommier ORCID
GR-CERTH	Anastasia Anastasiadou ORCID , Fotis Psomopoulos ORCID , Nikolaos Pechlivanis ORCID
GR-DUTH	Aristotelis C. Papageorgiou ORCID
GR-HCMR	Alexios Loukas, Evangelos Pafilis ORCID , Nefeli Venetsianou
IT-UOB	Giuseppe Defazio ORCID , Bruno Fosso ORCID
NL-WUR	Matthijs Brouwer ORCID
NO-NMBU	Arturo VeraPonce de Leon ORCID , Gareth Benjamin Gillard ORCID , Helle Tessand Baalsrud ORCID , Lars Grnvold ORCID , Thu-Hien To ORCID
PT-ITQB NOVA	M. Margarida Oliveira ORCID
SL-NIB	Kristina Gruden ORCID
UK-UNIOXF	Philippe Rocca-Serra ORCID
UK-ROTHAMSTED	Keywan Hassani-Pak ORCID